

The Effect of Light Pollution on Herbaceous Plants

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Abstract: Artificial light at night (ALAN) significantly affects plants, impacting physiological, morphological, biosynthetic, flowering, and stress-related processes. This study compared growth and photosynthetic responses of two invasive species in Hungary—the bohemian knotweed (*Fallopia x bohemica*) and annual fleabane (*Erigeron annuus*)—with two vegetable crops, tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) and pepper (*Capsicum annuum*), under natural outdoor conditions with and without light pollution. The invasive species were exposed to CFL lamps (3000K, 0.5 PAR) and the vegetable crops to amber LED lamps (3000K, 0.2 PAR) during night-time low-intensity illumination. Measurements included plant height, leaf dimensions, photosynthetic electron transport, PSII photochemical efficiency, net photosynthesis, and transpiration. Results showed that annual fleabane developed significantly larger leaves under light pollution, while bohemian knotweed leaf morphology remained unchanged. Both invasive species exhibited increased net photosynthesis and PSII efficiency under light pollution; however, bohemian knotweed showed signs of stress indicated by reduced electron transport efficiency and increased non-photochemical quenching. Contrarily, tomato and pepper demonstrated higher photosynthetic performance in non-polluted environments. Tomato showed no growth difference, while pepper had slightly larger biomass and leaves despite decreased photosynthetic parameters under light pollution. Sensitivity to light pollution varied by species origin and strategy. Invasive species displayed enhanced photosynthetic performance under nocturnal artificial light, partially translating to growth benefits, whereas ALAN inhibited performance in the two cultivated species.

Keywords: light pollution; photosynthetic activity; invasive plants; tomato.

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